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SOLUBILITY ENHANCEMENT OF EFAVIRENZ BY SOLID DISPERSION TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

In present investigation formulation of Efavirenz dispersion using Polymer like PEG 6000 and HPMC can be used to prepare inclusion complexes of Efavirenz with improved solubility of the drug. Phase solubility studied of drug with PEG 6000 illustrates the solubility enhancement. The phase solubility of pure drug, physical mixture and solid dispersion was found to be 66.12 and 57.21 $\mu\text{g}/\text{nm}$. respectively. FT-IR studied indicated the formation of true complex of Efavirenz and PEG6000 in 1:2 molar ratio prepared by solvent evaporation method. The dissolution of Efavirenz from inclusion complex prepared by fusion, solvent evaporation method was found to be higher than the pure drug and other prepared complexes. Enhancement of the solubility of Efavirenz PEG600 solvent evaporation complex was 96.76% in 90 min with 3 fold in its dissolution rate.

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INTRODUCTION

The Biopharmaceutical Classification System (BCS) is a guide for predicting the intestinal drug absorption provided by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration. This system restricts the prediction using the parameters solubility and intestinal permeability. The intestinal permeability classification is based on a comparison to the intravenous injection. Solubility is based on the highest-dose strength of an immediate release product. A drug is considered highly soluble when the highest dose strength is soluble in 250mL or less of aqueous media over the pH range of 1 to 7.5. The volume estimate of 250mL is derived from typical bioequivalence study protocols that prescribe administration of a drug product to fasting human volunteers with a glass of water.⁽¹⁻²⁾

Drug absorption from the GI tract can be limited by a variety of factors most significant contributor being poor aqueous solubility and poor membrane permeability of the drug molecule. When administered an active agent orally it must first dissolve in gastric and/orintestinal fluids before it can permeate the membranes of the GIT to reach systemiccirculation. Hence, two areas of pharmaceutical research that focus on improving the oralbioavailability of active agents include; enhancing of solubility and dissolution rate of poorlywater soluble drugs. The BCS is a scientific framework for classifying a drug substancebased on its aqueous solubility and intestinal permeability.

As for BCS class II & IV drugs rate limiting step is drug release from the dosage form andsolubility in gastric fluid and not the absorption, so increasing the solubility in turn increasethe bioavailability for BCS class II & IV drugs.^(3,4)

A solid dispersion is "the dispersion of one or more active ingredients in an inert carrier at solid-state prepared by melting (fusion), solvent or the melting-solvent method". The carrier used has traditionally been a watersoluble or water-miscible polymer such as polyethylene glycol (PEG) or polyvinylpyrrolidone(PVP) or low molecular weight materials such as urea, citric acid and mannitol. However, the proliferation of publications in the solid dispersions area has led to a broadening of these definitions to include water-insoluble matrices such as Gelucires⁽⁵⁾

Efavirenz is a non-nucleoside reverse transcriptaseinhibitor with activity against HIV. It is used with other antiretrovirals for combination therapy of HIV infection. Efavirenz is administered by mouth as capsules or tablets in an adult dose of 600 mg once daily, alternatively, it may be given as an oral solution in an adult dose of 720 mg once daily. Dose at bedtime is recommended during the first 2 to 4 weeks of therapy to improve tolerability. Doses (as capsules) for children over the age of 3 years are based on body weight, children weighing 13 to 14 kg are given 200 mg once daily, those weighing 15 to 19 kg, 250 mg once daily, those weighing 20 to 24 kg, 300 mg once daily, those weighing 25 to 32.4 kg, 350 mg once daily, those weighing 32.5 to 39 kg, 400 mg once daily and those weighing 40 kg or more, 600 mg once daily. Bioavailability of efavirenz from the oral solution is less than that from the capsule and so proportionately higher doses are used, the dose ranges which are again calculated in terms of body weight and depend on the age range.^(6,7)

MATERIALS AND METHOD-

Materials

Efavirenz was obtained as gift sample from Ciplapvt.Ltd.Mumbai Polyethylene Glycol 6000, obtained from M.J.Biopharm Ltd HPMC obtained from Titan Biotech Ltd,Bhiwadi(Rajasthan) Methanol, Hydrochloric Acid, Sodium lauryl sulfate purchased from Thomas baker, Mumbai. All the reagents and materials were of analytical or pharmacopoeia grade.

Method

Method of preparation of Efavirenz Solid Dispersion:

Preparation of Efavirenz Solid Dispersion with PEG6000 & HPMC.

Solid dispersion of Efavirenz were prepared with PEG 6000 &HPMC. The methods used for the preparation of Efavirenz with PEG are physical mixture, solvent evaporation method, and fusion method.

Physical Mixture:

The physical mixture were prepared by weighing the calculate amount of Efavirenz and the carrier and then mixing them in a glass mortar by triturating. The resultant physical mixture was passed through 44-mesh sieve and stored dessicator until used for further studies.⁽⁸⁾

Solvent Evaporation Method:

The required amount of Efavirenz and the carrier were dissolved with sufficient volume of methanol with continuous stirring. The solvent was then completely evaporated at 45⁰ C with continuous stirring to obtain dry mass. The dried was pulverized passed through 44 mesh sieve and dessicator until used for further studies.⁽⁹⁾

Fusion Method:

Accurately weighed amount of carrier was melted in a porcelain dish at 80-85⁰ C and to this calculated amount of Efavirenz was added with thorough mixing for 1-2 minutes followed by quick cooling. The dried mass was then pulverized passed through 44 mesh sieves and desiccator until used for further studies.⁽¹⁰⁻¹¹⁾

Table No 1: Preparation of Efavirenz Solid Dispersion with PEG6000.

Batches	Drug: Polymer	Batches	Drug : Polymer
EFZ:PEG _{PM1}	1:1	EFZ:HPMC _{PM1}	1:1
EFZ:PEG _{PM2}	1:2	EFZ:HPMC _{PM2}	1:2
EFZ:PEG _{PM3}	1:3	EFZ:HPMC _{PM3}	1:3
EFZ:PEG _{SD1}	1:1	EFZ:HPMC _{SD1}	1:1
EFZ:PEG _{SD2}	1:2	EFZ:HPMC _{SD2}	1:2
EFZ:PEG _{SD3}	1:3	EFZ:HPMC _{SD3}	1:3
EFZ:PEG _{FM1}	1:1	EFZ:HPMC _{FM1}	1:1
EFZ:PEG _{FM2}	1:2	EFZ:HPMC _{FM2}	1:2
EFZ:PEG _{FM3}	1:3	EFZ:HPMC _{FM3}	1:3

Evaluation of Solid Dispersions

Determination of Drug Content:

The drug content was calculated by dissolving drug, physical mixture and solid dispersion equivalent to 10 mg in a 100 ml volumetric flask volume was made up to the mark with methanol and assayed further by using UV double beam (Lab India UV3000⁺) spectrophotometer at 254nm. Three replicates were prepared, and the average drug content were estimated in the prepared solid dispersion by using following formula⁽¹²⁾

$$\text{Drug Content (\%)} = \frac{\text{EFZ}_{\text{act}}}{\text{EFZ}_{\text{sd}}} \times 100$$

Determination of phase solubility study:

The solubility of the drug was measured in the presence of 1% 2% and 3% up to 5% w/v polymer in Distilled water. An excess amount of the drug was then added to approximately 10 ml of either D.W or carrier solution in glass tube. The tube were kept under vibration for 24hr by using shaker. After reaching the equilibrium status. saturated solution were filter in whatman filter paper diluted with water and then assay UV- visible spectrophotometer⁽¹³⁾

Determination of percentage yield:

Percentage practical yields of all the formulations were calculated to know about percent yield or efficiency of the method chosen for the formulations. The formed solid dispersion were collected and weighed to determine the respective practical yields (P.Y).⁽¹⁴⁾

In –Vitro Dissolution Studies

The quantity of Solid Dispersion equivalent to EFZ was placed in dissolution medium. The dissolution study of dispersion was conducted using dissolution testing apparatus II (paddle method) in 900 ml of 2% W/V SLS solution at 37±0.5°C and at speed of 50 rpm. Aliquots of 5 ml was withdrawn at predetermined time interval and equivalent amount of fresh medium was replaced to maintain volume after each sampling and analyzed Spectrophotometrically at 246 nm against suitable blank using UV-visible Spectrophotometer . The sample were wrapped in muslin cloth and cumulative release were calculated by using PCP-Disso Software and dissolution data of EFZ,PEG 6000,HPMC .⁽¹⁵⁻¹⁶⁾

Compatibility study of Solid Dispersion

Infrared (FTIR) Studies

The solid dispersion were mixed separately with IR grade KBr in mortar and pestle in the ratio of 1:2 and placed in metallic superceeds by pressing with metallic rod pellets were obtained. The pellets were individually prepared for drug and polymer and were scanned over a wavenumber range of 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹ by diffuse Reflectance system in FTIR instrument Shimadzu, Japan (IR Affinity-1). The peaks corresponding to drug and polymers.

UV Interference Studies :

Scanning of solid dispersion was performed to evaluate whether there were any interference in UV detection of solid dispersion compared to control (drug) which can depict the drug polymer interaction. The UV interference of each solid dispersion was determined using powder equivalent to 10 mg of Efavirenz and was dissolved in 20 ml methanol using the mechanical shaker for 2 min. and to the solution obtained methanol was added and volume made to 50 ml. The solution was filtered through whatman filter paper no 42 and required dilutions were made and finally dilutions were scanned for determination of λ_{max} and 3 dimensional spectrums were obtained from UV WIN 2.0 Software compared with the spectrum of pure drug.⁽¹⁷⁾

Accelerated Stability Studies:

Stability study of formulation was carried out to point out any visual physical or chemical changes made in the formulation after storing it at elevated temperature and humidity condition. chemical and physical stability of SD_s formulation was assessed at 40±2°C and 75±5% RH per ICH Guidelines. SD_D formulation was filled in sealed vial with aluminum foil and stored for 3 month in stability chamber. sample were analyzed for physical parameter and drug content during time period of 3 months.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of drug content in solid dispersion and physical mixtures

The solid dispersions or physical mixture equivalent to 10 mg of Efavirenz were used to determine drug content. The drug content of solid dispersion and physical mixture is shown in fig.No.1.

Fig no.1 Drug content in Physical Mixture and Solid Dispersion.

Phase solubility studies:

The phase solubility data according to Higuchi and Connor was shown below and based on the data the selection of the ratios for final formulations was done. The criterion observed was increment of drug solubility with polymer concentration.

Fig No : 2 Effect of concentrations of PEG 6000 & HPMC on solubility of Efavirenz (\pm S).

Percentage yields

The percentage yields of various formulations of solid dispersion were determined and it was observed that kneading method yielded higher % yields than fusion method. The highest yield was observed in EFZ:PEG_{SD2}

Fig No 3 .Percentage yields of SDs.

Dissolution studies:

Efavirenz solid dispersion presented better dissolution performance over corresponding physical mixtures and the pure drug. This may be due to an improved wettability of drug particles, a significant reduction in particle size during the formation of solid dispersion, and the intrinsically higher rate of dissolution of the soluble polymer component of the solid dispersion. The dissolution profiles of Efavirenz , solid dispersions and fusion method.

Table no 2. In vitro Dissolution Profile of EFZ.

Sr.No	Batch	Cumulative % release at different time interval in minute							
		0	05	10	15	20	30	45	60
1	Efavirenz	0	1.26	3.73	4.27	6.17	11.87	20.52	27.10
2	EFZ:PEGSD1	0	3.19	5.89	8.91	13.24	18.39	29.65	39.62
3	EFZ:PEGSD2	0	8.53	11.91	15.34	21.56	30.42	39.71	45.4
4	EFZ:PEGSD3	0	14.36	18.48	24.13	31.51	39.0	48.23	56.91
5	EFZ:PEGFS1	0	4.12	6.52	9.36	14.3	19.6	30.5	40.5
6	EFZ:PEGFD2	0	9.11	12.23	16.9	22.6	31.56	40.73	46.52
7	EFZ:PEGFD3	0	15.0	19.6	25.67	33.54	40.87	49.23	57.64
8	EFZ:HPMC SD1	0	4.5	6.78	9.6	15.3	18.6	30.74	40.64
9	EFZ:HPMC SD2	0	8.64	12.87	17.65	22.87	30.74	40.84	45.47
10	EFZ:HPMC SD3	00	14.99	17.43	25.74	32.43	39.67	45.45	57.3
11	EFZ:HPMC FM1	00	4.88	6.8	10.45	13.65	17.54	29.6	37.86
12	EFZ:HPMC FM2	000	9.54	12.63	16.83	22.8	33.85	40.12	45.93
13	EFZ:HPMC FM3	00	15.83	19.32	24.22	32.53	40.43	48.95	57.33

Compatibility between Drug and Excipients

Fig No 3 FTIR Spectrum of Efavirenz.

Fig No.4 FTIR Spectrum of physical mixture of EFZ: PEG.

Fig No 5 : FTIR Spectrum of physical mixture of EFZ:HPMC.

Table No 8: Stability studies of SD_s.

Day	Drug Content	
	Solid Dispersion EFZPEG _{SD2}	Solid Dispersion EFZHPMC _{SD2}
	40 ⁰ ±2 ⁰ C/75%±RH	
0	99.45± 0.6	98.23±0.12
30	98.54±0.23	97.65±0.54
60	97.67±0.45	96.86±0.65
90	96.76±0.12	96.45±0.2

CONCLUSION

The poor dissolution of water insoluble drug as for long had been a problem in a formulation of oral dosage form. This limit such as absorption and Bioavailability. Several approaches have been followed in improving solubility of the drug, one of them is solid dispersion to increase the solubility and bioavailability Efavirenz can be formulated in the form of complexes with carrier such as PEG 6000 and HPMC. The inclusion complexes of Efavirenz prepared by solvent evaporation method were subjected to short term accelerated stability studies had no appreciable change in this physical appearance, drug content value and dissolution profile were observed. Enhancement of the solubility of Efavirenz PEG600 solvent evaporation complex was 96.76% in 90 min with 3 fold in its dissolution rate. Hence from the above result it can be concluded that PEG 6000 and HPMC can used to formulate fast releasing formulations of drug.

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